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Immune system and COVID-19

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

Taking into account that early adaptive immune responses might correlate with better clinical outcomes, it is important to emphasize that healthy immune system plays an important role in the treatment and possibly in the prevention of COVID-19 disease. Factors that can contribute to the better immune system functionality are healthy balanced diet (with addition of vitamins and trace elements if necessary), moderate physical exercise, ingestion of polyphenols and natural antivirals, protection of nasal and oropharyngeal mucosa with mucosal care and protection products, and smoking cessation.

INTRODUCTION

The SARS-CoV-2 is a β -coronavirus, which is enveloped non-segmented positive-sense RNA virus (subgenus *sarbecovirus*, subfamily *Orthocoronavirinae*¹).

It was found that the genome sequence of SARS-CoV-2 is 96.2% identical to a bat CoV RaTG13, whereas it shares 79.5% identity to SARS-CoV. Based on virus genome sequencing results and evolutionary analysis, bat has been suspected as natural host of virus origin, and SARS-CoV-2 might be transmitted from bats via unknown intermediate hosts to infect humans².

The clinical symptoms of COVID-19 patients include fever, cough, fatigue and a small population of patients appeared gastrointestinal infection symptoms³.

IMMUNE RESPONSES ON SARS-CoV-2 INFECTION

Thevarajan and coworkers published a report of the kinetics of immune responses in relation to clinical and virological features of a patient with mild-to-moderate coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) that required hospitalization. Increased antibody-secreting cells (ASCs), follicular helper T cells (T_{FH} cells), activated $CD4^+$ T cells and $CD8^+$ T cells and immunoglobulin M (IgM) and IgG antibodies that bound the COVID-19-causing coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 were detected in blood before symptomatic recovery. These immunological changes persisted for at least 7 days following full resolution of symptoms. This study indicates that robust multi-factorial immune responses can be elicited to the newly emerged virus SARS-CoV-2 and, similar to the avian H7N9 disease early adaptive immune responses might correlate with better clinical outcomes⁴.

Taking into account that early adaptive immune responses might correlate with better clinical outcomes, it is important to emphasize that healthy immune system plays an important role in the treatment and possibly in the prevention of COVID-19 disease.

Factors that can contribute to the better immune system functionality are:

1. Healthy balanced diet with addition of vitamins and trace elements supplements if necessary. Viral, bacterial and fungal infections, especially the severe ones, can cause hypovitaminosis of multiple vitamins (vitamin B complex, A, C, E, D, and K). The same, patients with hypovitaminoses are more susceptible for the development of infections. Vitamins that play an important role in immune system functioning are especially vitamin A, D, C and E, niacin (B3), pantothenic acid (B5) and pyridoxine (B6)⁵⁻¹². Zinc is an essential micronutrient that is involved in the regulation of the innate and adaptive immune responses¹³.

2. Moderate physical exercise (during pandemic it is best to perform short-lasting outdoor physical exercises secluded, when it is sunny, because UV light is a natural virucidal agent¹⁴). Nieman and coworkers concluded in the study that acute exercise is an immune system adjuvant that improves defense activity and metabolic health. Data support a clear inverse relationship between moderate exercise training and illness risk. Exercise training has an anti-inflammatory influence mediated through multiple pathways. Illness risk is increased in athletes during periods of intensified training and

competition. Increased carbohydrate and polyphenol intake is an effective nutritional strategy for immune support. Habitual exercise improves immune regulation, delaying the onset of age-related dysfunction¹⁵.

3. Ingestion of polyphenols. Polyphenols, one of many categories of natural substances, exhibit a range of biological activities. They promote immunity to foreign pathogens via various pathways. Different immune cells express multiple types of polyphenol receptors that recognize and allow cellular uptake of polyphenols, which subsequently activate signaling pathways to initiate immune responses. The polyphenols curcumin and epigallocatechin gallate can induce epigenetic changes in cells. Polyphenols can be used to regulate intestinal mucosal immune responses, allergic diseases, and antitumour immunity¹⁶.

Polyphenols include flavonoids, phenolic acids, and stilbenoids, which are ubiquitously produced in plants and exist either as free aglycones or in a state of esterification with glucose and other carbohydrates (glycosides¹⁷).

A study showed that *in vitro* **resveratrol** (polyphenol from grape seeds and red wine) has some anti-viral effect on coronaviruses¹⁸.

4. Natural antivirals. Studies showed that **glycyrrhizin** from **liquorice root** has some anti-viral effect on coronaviruses, what opens the question can glycyrrhizin be used as experimental drug for the treatment of COVID-19 patients or can this compound lead to the development of similar, more potent drugs^{19, 20}. Other potent antivirals are oregano, ginger, sage, basil, fennel, garlic, lemon balm, peppermint, rosemary, *Echinacea purpurea*, sambucus, astragalus, ginseng, dandelion²¹, thyme, hyssop, sandalwood, and star anise, but these were not yet tested for their activity against coronaviruses.

5. Protection of nasal and oropharyngeal mucosa with mucosal care and protection products.

6. Smoking cessation. Smoking impacts both innate and adaptive immunity and plays dual roles in regulating immunity by either exacerbation of pathogenic immune responses or attenuation of defensive immunity. Adaptive immune cells affected by smoking mainly include T helper cells (Th1/Th2/Th17), CD4+CD25+ regulatory T cells, CD8+ T cells, B cells and memory T/B lymphocytes while innate immune cells impacted by smoking are mostly dendritic cells, macrophages and natural killer cells²².

CONCLUSION

Taking into account that early adaptive immune responses might correlate with better clinical outcomes, it is important to emphasize that healthy immune system plays an important role in the treatment and possibly in the prevention of COVID-19 disease. Factors that can contribute to the better immune system functionality are healthy balanced diet (with addition of vitamins and trace elements if necessary), moderate physical exercise, ingestion of polyphenols and natural antivirals, protection of nasal and oropharyngeal mucosa with mucosal care and protection products, and smoking cessation.

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